

A method for requirements change identification in software ecosystems based on open innovation and CrowdRE

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Abstract

Context: Software ecosystems (SECO) have introduced complexity in requirements change management due to their open and dynamic nature. In SECO, multiple actors collaborate through several organizational boundaries and can form distinct crowds in the ecosystem.

Objective: This work proposes SECO-RCI, a method to assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and crowd-based requirements engineering (CrowdRE)

Method: We applied Design Science to build the SECO-RCI and conducted a focus group and a single case study to evaluate their acceptance.

Results: In the focus group, we gathered perceptions and suggestions on the method from five experts with practical experience in requirements management in SECO. In the single case study, we involved one professional who applied SECO-RCI to a real-world scenario.

Conclusions: The results demonstrated that our method can effectively support professionals in requirements change identification in SECO. Employing SECO-RCI can improve understanding of the characteristics of SECO that differentiate it from other software development contexts. Using SECO-RCI also enables more effective requirements communication among the multiple actors of distinct crowds of a SECO regarding requirements change.

Keywords: Software Ecosystems, SECO, Requirements Change Management, Open Innovation, Crowd-based Requirements Engineering

1. Introduction

Requirements changes are inevitable in software development [1, 2]. They may arise at any stage of the software development process due to different internal and external factors, e.g., customer needs, technological changes, market change, budget change, and global competition [3, 4]. Dynamic requirements change is among the principal difficulties that software businesses face [5]. According to Ali and Lai [6], the effect of requirements changes is beneficial for a project if changes are addressed appropriately at the right time; otherwise, they may result in project failure. Requirements change naturally impact the project's cost, quality, and schedule, creating additional work in design and coding [7, 1]. Therefore, it is not just important but crucial for the success of the final product to understand and manage requirements change during software development [3, 5, 4, 8].

In modern software development, software projects are increasingly complex, and professionals encounter several challenges in handling requirements change [9]. Studies highlighted these challenges in different software development contexts, such as agile development [10], global software development (GSD) [4], development and operations (DevOps) [11], and software ecosystems (SECO) [12]. SECO are becoming a predominant software development context and are an integral part of modern software development [13, 14]. They are complex systems that involve multiple software components, platforms, and developers interacting within open and dynamic environments that go beyond the limits of a single organization [15]. SECO enable multiple actors and stakeholders from different organizations to collaborate and contribute to the ecosystem with different elements to develop, maintain, and evolve a complex software system [16, 17, 14]. However, changes to one product can have ripple effects on several others in a SECO, introduce conflicts, and be unexpected and disruptive [12].

Managing requirements change in SECO is challenging due to scalability, mismatched priorities, heterogeneous levels and areas of expertise, and limits on communication and collaboration [18, 13, 19]. Moreover, there is a lack of guidelines for the RE process in SECO [20]. Software professionals often face challenges in requirements change identification due to the openness and dynamism of SECO with the interdependence between multiple products and the integration between them and the common technological platform [21]. Bogart et al. [12] stated that traditional approaches to centralized change control or change management (e.g., change control panels and roadmap-

ping) break with the dynamic and distributed nature of SECO. Therefore, meeting the expectations of multiple users in SECO requires new approaches that involve this multitude of stakeholders in requirements engineering (RE) activities [22].

In response to these challenges, we introduce SECO-RCI (Requirements Change Identification in Software Ecosystems). SECO-RCI is a method designed to assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and crowd-based RE (CrowdRE). In SECO, open innovation is a focus area concerned with sharing knowledge across the ecosystem to feed external developers with new possibilities for improvement [15]. Therefore, user participation is essential for the success of open innovation in SECO [23]. Users in SECO often form distinct crowds comprised of a large heterogeneous base of users who give requirements on multiple channels with multiple stakeholders [24]. Requirements change management in SECO can benefit from the CrowdRE. CrowdRE is an emerging RE paradigm that uses automated or semi-automated approaches to gather and analyze information from a crowd to derive valid user requirements [25, 26].

We performed two studies to evaluate the feasibility of SECO-RCI. In the first study, we conducted a focus group of five experts with theoretical and practical experience in requirements management in SECO. We presented the structure and content of the SECO-RCI to these professionals to gather their perceptions and suggestions on the method. The second study involved a single case study in a SECO of an organization with more than seventy research centers specialized in different fields of knowledge focused on applied science. This last study focused on the experiences of one professional who applied SECO-RCI using a real-world scenario and the potential impact of the method on their work. The results indicate the acceptance of SECO-RCI. The evaluations further unveil the SECO-RCI's potential in facilitating requirements change identification and requirements communication. Furthermore, our research highlights the need for technical knowledge in some feedback channels so that changes in requirements are identified more specifically for different projects in a SECO.

Summarizing, the main contributions of this study are:

- The introduction of SECO-RCI, a method designed for requirements change identification in SECO;
- A first evaluation of the SECO-RCI feasibility by a focus group with

five experts to collect their perceptions of the method from an intuitive perspective;

- A second evaluation of the SECO-RCI feasibility by a single case study with one professional who applied SECO-RCI in a large real-world scenario and provided their opinion from a practical perspective; and
- Finally, a discussion of the main findings and implications of SECO-RCI usage by researchers and practitioners.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the background whereas Section 3 shows related work; Section 4 details our research method; Section 5 introduces SECO-RCI; Section 6 presents the results of the evaluation conducted through two distinct studies; Section 7 presents a discussion of the results, implications for practitioners and researchers, and lessons learned; Section 8 discusses the threats and limitations of this work; and, finally, Section 9 concludes this article.

2. Background

This section provides the background on four topics directly related to this work: SECO, requirements change management in SECO, open innovation in SECO, and CrowdRE in SECO.

2.1. *Software Ecosystems*

According to Barbosa et al. [27] and Manikas [28], the research about SECO started in 2003 with Messerschmitt and Szyperski’s book [29]. Since then, SECO have become an active research topic in software engineering and literature has presented SECO definitions from different perspectives [30, 31, 32, 28]. According to Mens and Roover [33], Manikas [28] combined all the perspectives used in other SECO definitions into a single all-encompassing definition. Manikas [28] defined SECO as the development of multiple products derived from a common technological platform based on a central architecture integrating other systems and forming a network of actors and artifacts.

There is a significant body of research on SECO and common characteristics have been identified in several works [27, 34, 35, 36, 37]. According to Lettner et al. [35], there is a growing agreement about SECO’s general characteristics. We summarized the main SECO characteristics in Table 1.

Table 1: SECO characteristics.

Characteristic	Source
Internal and external developers	[27, 35, 36, 37]
Common technological platform	[35, 36].
Keystone	[27, 35]
Platform enabling external contributions	[35, 36]
Variability-enabled architectures	[27, 35, 36]
Shared core assets	[35]
Automated and tool-supported product derivation	[35, 36]
Tools, frameworks and patterns	[35, 36]
Distribution channel	[35, 36]
Openness	[27]
Innovation processes	[27, 38, 36]
Co-evolution of software projects	[32, 34, 27, 36]

Jansen [15] highlighted that the concept of SECO has impacted the platform business and research world. For the author, over a short period, scientists and companies conceptualized and realized SECO in a way that significantly affected society and the software industry. Manikas [28] classified SECO into three types: (i) proprietary (PSECO): SECO based on proprietary contributions, typically protected by intellectual property management processes, e.g., platform as a service and e-commerce ecosystems; (ii) open source (OSSECO): SECO based on contributions which are typically open to the rest of the actors or public, e.g., Eclipse Foundation and Apache Foundation; or (iii) hybrid: SECO that supports both proprietary and open source contributions, e.g. iOS SECO can use proprietary strategies such as the app store and source code repository to drive policy on the technology platform and open source strategies for community engagement such as tools, submission, and publication contributions.

2.2. Requirements Change Management in SECO

Change is an intrinsic characteristic of the software engineering discipline compared to other engineering disciplines and a challenging aspect of the RE process [3, 39]. Jayatilleke et al. [3] claimed that it is anticipated that requirements will change during a project life cycle, and such volatility constitutes one of the top ten risks to successful project development. Requirements volatility is “the tendency of requirements to change over time in response to the evolving needs of customers, stakeholders, the organization and the work environment” [40, 11]. A requirements change is an addition/modification/deletion/bug fix or combination of these in terms of functional and non-functional requirements presented in any form [41].

Requirements change management can be defined as the management of requirements change during the RE process, system development, and maintenance process [3]. It is a collaboration-driven process that requires communication and coordination between several stakeholders to be successful [42]. Requirements change management enables software development organizations to deliver quality products per clients' expectations [42]. Requirements change identification is an important sub-process of the requirements change management process, which indicates why, by whom, and when a requirements change is required [3, 43]. The next requirements change management sub-processes will be based on the correct identification of the problem space, as well as requirements change [3]. Understanding what needs to be changed is a significant factor in the requirements change management process that helps clarify how the demanded change can be implemented [43]. According to Jayatilleke et al. [3], there are two major activities within requirements change identification: requirements change elicitation and requirements change representation.

In SECO, the ideal recipient for a given request generally changes over time, making it necessary to periodically rethink how requirements (or requirements change) travel through software organizations and which roles are responsible for seeking alignment of objectives [21]. Furthermore, how, when, and by whom changes are made in a SECO are subject to (often implicit) negotiation between multiple actors in the ecosystem [21]. According to Bogart et al. [12], the burden of change can be borne by different SECO actors: (i) the keystone can decide how to make a change, can invest additional efforts to facilitate the adoption of the change, or can decide to accept opportunity costs by not making any changes; (ii) external developers can regularly monitor changes to their dependencies and try to influence their development, or they can rework their own products; and (iii) users may encounter defects if changes are not made or installation difficulties if products in the repository become incompatible. Therefore, consultation with all these actors can bring benefits to the requirements change management in SECO.

2.3. Open Innovation in SECO

Open innovation assumes that companies should use internal and external ideas and paths to market as they look to advance their technology [44]. According to Valença et al. [45], organizations have formed SECO through a platformisation process following an open innovation trend. SECO influence

fundamental aspects such as openness, collaboration, and innovation in software development [15]. The openness implied by open innovation and SECO makes a firm’s formerly closed borders permeable for interaction and influence from new stakeholders [46]. In this scenario, Papatheocharous et al. [47] stated that it is necessary to define processes that promote open innovation in SECO.

Several works have addressed the relationship between open innovation, SECO and RE [48, 49, 50, 51]. According to Linåker et al. [46], SECO affect how RE processes are structured, as these processes are traditionally centralized and limited to a defined set of stakeholders. Linåker et al. [46] also stated that RE has moved to become more decentralized and collaborative with an evolving set of stakeholders in SECO. For Linåker et al. [48], RE can benefit from the implicit changes that open innovation offers in SECO and must adapt to this new context. Linåker and Wnuk [50] claimed that open innovation had blurred the boundaries between internal and external contexts in SECO and extended the scope of requirements activities to entire ecosystems. Moreover, continuously implementing external requirements helps create more value for products and services in SECO [51].

2.4. CrowdRE in SECO

CrowdRE is an emerging paradigm that includes all approaches that engage a “crowd” of a software product’s current and potential users to perform RE tasks or provide requirements-relevant information [25, 26]. It is an umbrella term for applying (semi-)automated approaches for collecting and analyzing information from a crowd to derive validated user requirements [26]. According to Groen and Ochs [52] and Santos et al. [53], a promising approach in CrowdRE is considering user feedback about software products. User feedback is an important resource in modern software development, often containing requirements that help address user concerns and desires for one or more software products [54]. Requirements management considers user feedback relevant because it validates and discovers requirements change during the continuous software evolution [55, 56, 57, 58].

In SECO, user feedback is typically used to guide the development of new features, bug fixes, and overall improvements to the product [59]. However, distinct crowds give requirements on multiple channels with multiple stakeholders in SECO, which poses demands beyond those found by a single product owner [24]. Johnson et al. [24] highlighted CrowdRE-related challenges that arise in a SECO context, such as the need to motivate feedback

across several distinct 'crowds' of users that influence monitoring the entire ecosystem's health. Villela et al. [60] and Villela et al. [61] mentioned CrowdRE as an approach contributing to ubiquitous RE in the SECO context. Jansen [15] highlighted creating open requirements management systems and constantly listening to the requirements and feedback from extenders in the field as important tasks to incorporate wishes from partners into a product or platform within a SECO. According to Ghimire et al. [14], analyzing SECO reviews is difficult because distinguishing whether feedback refers to a single partner application, multiple applications, or the SECO common technological platform can be challenging.

3. Related Work

Few studies have addressed the topic of requirements change in SECO. Among them, we highlight the work of Bogart et al. [12], which performed a multiple case study of three SECO with different tooling and philosophies toward change (Eclipse, R/CRAN, and Node.js/npm) to understand how developers make decisions about change and change-related costs and what practices, tooling, and policies are used. The results of this work illustrate that there is value in making community values and accepted tradeoffs explicit and transparent to resolve conflicts and negotiate change-related costs. Another work was of the Matute et al. [19], which investigated software changes in SECO. According to the authors, managing changes in SECO is difficult because SECO are complex social systems that struggle with scale, mismatched priorities, heterogeneous levels and areas of expertise, and limits on communication and collaboration. Matute et al. [19] identified four social challenges of rolling out software changes in SECO: scale, priorities, expertise, and visibility. The results of this work illustrate that SECO produce several social barriers to deploying changes, but there are opportunities to automate and reduce duplicated effort in this software development context.

Several methods are available for different requirements change management phases in different software development contexts. Lim and Finkelstein [62] proposed a method to anticipate change in the traditional software development context. It separates requirements into layers that change at relatively different rates during requirements documentation. The results show that the method proposed by Lim and Finkelstein [62] accurately anticipates the relative volatility of the requirements. Jayatilleke et al. [3] presented a method of requirements change analysis based on changes initiated at higher

levels in the traditional software development context. It consists of analyzing the change using functions, identifying the change difficulty, and identifying the dependencies using a matrix. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Jayatilleke et al. [3] contributes to the identification of conflicts and dependencies between requirement changes, allocation of priority to changes, and understanding of the difficulty of change.

Amaral and de Franco Rosa [63] presented a method for assessing the potential impact of requirements changes of agile methodologies-based projects. This method consists of the use of requirement traceability and effort prediction on scope changes to benefit agile methodologies. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Amaral and de Franco Rosa [63] provides a potential impact rate on scope changes in agile methodologies-based projects. Ali and Lai [6] presented a graph-based method for requirements change management in the GSD context. This method consists of understanding the changes required between different GSD sites to be established, performing a change analysis concerning the development work, which might be either directly or indirectly affected by the changes, and finalizing the changes that will be made between GSD sites. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Ali and Lai [6] facilitates stakeholders in managing requirements changes for GSD better than the existing methods could.

Our study differs from others by proposing a method for requirements change identification in SECO. Previous studies that dealt with changes to requirements in SECO did not suggest any approach to dealing with requirements change in this context. They only analyzed requirements changes in SECO through case studies or identified related challenges. Furthermore, these studies highlighted that more research is needed to investigate requirements change management in SECO. The other previous studies that proposed methods for requirements change management were related to different software development contexts and were not focused on identifying requirements change in SECO. We understand that these methods can be used in SECO. However, they were not created considering the SECO characteristics detailed in Section 2.

4. Research Method

The development of the proposed solution was guided by the principles of Design Science [64], a methodology commonly used in software engineering and information systems areas to design, evaluate, and refine software arti-

facts. The central artifact of our work is a method, and we used to construct it the method engineering [65], which is “the engineering discipline to design, construct and adapt methods, techniques, and tools for the development of information systems” [65, 66]. Figure 1 shows the four main steps of our research method: Step 1 - Problem investigation, Step 2 - Definition of the objective, Step 3 - Solution design, and Step 4 - Evaluation. The following subsections provide detailed descriptions of each step and their respective sub-steps, while Section 5 outlines the method developed in Step 3, and Section 6 reports the results from Step 4.

Figure 1: Our research method.

4.1. Step 1 — Problem Investigation

This step consists of understanding and describing the problem to be addressed and identifying the needs and challenges that motivate the research [64]. It includes observing and analyzing the current context and identifying gaps or opportunities for improvement that justify the need to create a new solution or enhance an existing one [64]. To do so, we conducted a systematic mapping study (SMS) [67] and performed two field studies [68, 69].

We carried out a SMS to gather evidence and explore the state of the art of requirements management in SECO [67]. This SMS aimed to identify requirements management characteristics in SECO and approaches used to support it. By analyzing the 29 primary studies selected in the work, we noticed that: (i) there are still open questions about requirements change in SECO; (ii) requirements management is one of the least covered RE processes in studies on SECO; (iii) there is a lack of guidelines for executing it; (iv) the open innovation paradigm is explored in requirements management in SECO and that it positively impacts requirements change management; (v) requirements management in SECO involves distinct crowds that include different

types of users, external developers, and the keystone; and (vi) CrowdRE can help address requirements management challenges in SECO.

The first field study was based on interviews with 21 professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO to identify open innovation practices in this context [68]. As a result, we identified 10 open innovation practices used to support requirements management in SECO and 14 communication channels used to receive/provide requirements (or requirements change) from/to external actors. Our main results showed that the use of multiple open communication channels by internal and external actors allows the use of different open innovation practices in this context, such as crowdsourcing, co-creation, collaboration, cooperation, and customer immersion. These practices provide knowledge sharing across the ecosystem and affect requirements change management in this context.

The second field study was based on interviews with 20 professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO to investigate whether and how user feedback from a crowd is considered in requirements management in SECO [69]. As a result, we identified that professionals usually considered user feedback from distinct crowds in requirements management activities in SECO. We also identified ten mechanisms used to gather user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO and six approaches to analyze this feedback. Moreover, we noticed that user feedback from a crowd influences requirements change management in SECO, making it more open and collaborative. We also realized that the continuous flow of user feedback makes CrowdRE possible in SECO.

4.2. Step 2 - Definition of Objective

Based on the results from Step 1, we defined that our solution should assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO. As a key requirement, we defined that our solution must be adaptable, i.e., it can be customized regardless of the type of SECO. This requirement was defended because different SECO types have nuances and specific characteristics. Another requirement for the solution is to leverage the open, dynamic, and distributed nature of SECO. In other words, our solution must consider the open innovation practices applied in SECO and the use of (semi)automated approaches to identify requirements changes from distinct crowds in SECO's multiple feedback channels (CrowdRE).

4.3. Step 3 — Solution Design

We developed a method called SECO-RCI to meet the solution objectives defined in Step 2. A method can be defined as an approach to perform a software/systems development project based on a specific way of thinking, consisting of guidelines, rules, and heuristics [65, 66]. A method is structured systematically regarding development activities, with corresponding development work products and developer roles [65, 66]. Precisely, the method’s outcomes inform a requirements change requests list. These requirements change requests are identified in multiple SECO user feedback channels through user feedback of distinct crowds, including internal and external actors of SECO. In other words, our goal is not to introduce specific techniques for requirements change identification, given the plethora of existing solutions for these purposes. Instead, we aim to assist professionals in implementing these techniques, guided by a systematic approach focused on requirements change identification based on open innovation practices and CrowdRE in an open, dynamic, and distributed environment as SECO.

To design our method, we based on SECO-RM, a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO [70]. Through a robust theoretical foundation, we developed SECO-RM, encompassing 43 concepts of requirements management in SECO and their relationships, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the subject. Section 5 details SECO-RCI.

4.4. Step 4 — Evaluation

In this research, our focus is on the method’s acceptance by experts and professionals. Hence, we seek to understand how SECO-RCI is perceived by experts and used by professionals to gain insights into its usefulness and ease of use. By gathering feedback and insights from experts and practitioners, we aim to investigate the feasibility of SECO-RCI as a novel artifact to improve requirements change identification in SECO. We conducted a focus group with experts and a single case study in the software industry to evaluate SECO-RCI. In the first study (*Study #1*), the method was introduced to the participants, followed by a group discussion to collect their perceptions of the method from an intuitive perspective. In the second study (*Study #2*), a participant employed SECO-RCI based on a realistic case of SECO. Then, they exposed their opinions from a practical perspective.

For both evaluation studies, we developed a guide with questions and topics that must be addressed [71]. We defined primary questions that could be answered objectively using a Likert scale to capture a general perception

from the participant about a specific aspect. Such closed-ended questions served as gateways to facilitate open-ended responses. Therefore, with each participant’s response, we prompted follow-up with questions such as “*Why?*”, “*Why do you think so?*”, “*Can you elaborate on that?*” and others to continue gathering information as needed. This approach helps us to deep into the participants’ thoughts, providing richer context and understanding beyond the initial response. Moreover, it encourages participants to reflect upon their answers, revealing additional insights [72].

Our interview guide included questions to evaluate the method’s usefulness and ease of use. By doing so, we address important factors that play a significant role in the acceptance of the method. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [73] inspired us to do so. TAM is a well-established information systems model that explains how users accept and use a particular technology. It declares that perceived usefulness and ease of use primarily influence technology acceptance. As Davis [73] explained, perceived usefulness is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will enhance their job performance. On the other hand, perceived ease of use is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will be free of effort. Even if an individual perceives a technology to be useful, its use could be hindered if perceived as too complex or requiring excessive effort.

4.4.1. Study #1

The first study’s dynamic involved introducing the method to participants and detailing all their activities in a focus group to obtain expert feedback. Focus groups are qualitative research methods that use group interviews to collect information based on participant communication and interaction [74]. We decided to adopt the focus group method since it is an efficient empirical approach for obtaining rich qualitative insights and feedback from experts and practitioners [75]. This method facilitates the exchange of ideas and experiences between participants, allowing people to explore their knowledge and perceptions on a given topic within a limited period [74]. Moreover, it enables the researcher to focus specifically on the research topic and has been successfully adopted in software engineering research [74]. To set up the focus group, we followed the activities proposed in Kontio et al. [74]: definition of the problem to investigate, selection of participants, data collection, execution of focus group, and data analysis.

Definition of the Problem to Investigate. The focus group aims to gather perceptions about the SECO-RCI method from an intuitive perspective. The SECO-RCI method must be presented and demonstrated to participants. In the focus group, we will focus on understanding participants' perceptions of the method's clarity and understandability, ease of use, usefulness, potential to reduce effort, completeness, intended use, and adaptability. These criteria help assess the method's feasibility for the intended users and their context according to experts' perspectives. By gathering expert opinions, the evaluation can capture their subjective experiences and perspectives, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. This feedback is crucial in guiding enhancements and adjustments to increase its chances of successful adoption. Hence, we defined the following research question: **RQ1** - *How is the acceptance of the SECO-RCI method among experts in the field? (RQ1)*

Selection of Participants. A focus group is sensitive to the experience and perspective of the participants. For this reason, the participant selection process is critical to its success [74]. We established the following participant selection criteria: (i) participants must have a PhD; (ii) participants must have experience in requirements management and SECO. We used convenience sampling to select participants for our study based on their being nearby and available [76]. We contacted experts in requirements management in SECO from our network via email and other communication channels (WhatsApp and LinkedIn). We sent invitations to seven experts, and five of them accepted to participate in the focus group. According to Shull et al. [77], the size of a focus group can vary from 3 to 12 participants. Hennink and Kaiser [78] conducted a recent systematic literature review on sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research and identified that saturation can be reached within a narrow range of 4–8 participants in focus groups.

In summary, all participants have PhD in computer science and more than nine years of professional experience in requirements management and SECO. Moreover, three participants have practical experience dealing with requirements change in SECO. Table 2 presents the participants' profiles.

Data Collection. In addition to the data collected during the focus group session, we used an electronic questionnaire for data collection. We defined primary questions that could be answered objectively using a Likert scale to capture a general perception from the participants about a specific aspect. We formulated seven statements for this study, using a 5-point

Table 2: SECO characteristics.

ID	Academic degree	Experience in years in requirements management	Experience in years in SECO
P1	PhD	15	14
P2	PhD	10	10
P3	PhD	20	9
P4	PhD	25	10
P5	PhD	20	14

Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Partially Agree, Neutral, Partially Disagree, and Strongly Disagree) to gather participants' perceptions of the SECO-RCI method. Then, we will encourage the participants to delve deep into their answers by asking follow-up questions to gain a more comprehensive understanding. Table 3 lists the statements of this study.

Table 3: Study #1 Statements.

ID	Statement	Aspect	Description
S1	The method and its activities are easy to understand.	Clarity and understanding	It refers to how easily a participant can understand the method and how clear its activities and related outputs are to them.
S2	The method activities are easy to perform.	Ease of use	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would be free from difficulty.
S3	The method is useful.	Usefulness	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would produce desirable outcomes.
S4	Using this method would reduce the effort to requirements change identification in SECO.	Potential to reduce effort	It refers to the perception of how much the method can decrease the amount of work or effort required to accomplish a goal.
S5	All method activities are necessary and enough.	Completeness	It refers to having all necessary activities needed to achieve a goal.
S6	I will use this method if I have the opportunity.	Intention of use	It refers to the likelihood that a participant plans to use the method in the future.
S7	The method is adaptable to all SECO types	Adaptability	It refers to the degree to which the framework can be adjusted to different SECO types.

Execution of Focus Group. Considering the different regional locations of the participants, the focus group was carried out using Google Meet¹ as a video conferencing tool. This tool provides greater flexibility in participation and allows adaptation of the schedules of those involved, making collaboration between all participants more viable, regardless of their different time zones. As a previous step to the execution of the focus group, we sent a file

¹<https://meet.google.com/>

with the SECO-RCI method description [71] to the participants a few days before holding the focus group.

The focus group was held in a 90-minute virtual session. In addition to the five participants, the first author of this paper was present to be the moderator of the focus group. The session was recorded with the permission of the participants. The structure of the session was as follows: (i) introduction of the moderator and participants; (ii) clarification about the study context; (iii) presentation of study goal; (iv) presentation of the structure and content of the SECO-RCI method; (v) analysis of the use of the SECO-RCI method to identify requirement changes in SECO; and (vi) discussion related to statements presented in Table 3.

Data Analysis. In this focus group, we aimed to evaluate the method’s acceptance among experts with theoretical and practical experience. We drew inspiration from TAM constructs to formulate the statements and perform a qualitative analysis. By doing so, we benefited from robust theoretical foundations enriched by years of research and empirical validation. This approach allows us to capture the participants’ perceptions while benefiting from TAM’s theoretical solid grounding. We will record and transcribe the focus group for further analysis. We will employ open coding procedures to support the analysis of participants’ responses. This systematic approach allows us to analyze the responses and identify common themes and patterns. Open coding offers a structured way to understand the raw data, enabling us to categorize the responses based on their key elements, contributing to a proper data interpretation [79].

4.4.2. Study #2

The second study’s dynamic involved applying the SECO-RCI method in a real SECO to evaluate its acceptance from a practical perspective through a single case study. Case studies are one of the most common approaches used in the software engineering domain to artifact evaluation [80]. They are empirical investigations that examine a contemporary event in depth and within its context [81]. The case study design must comprise case study selection and preparation to provide generalizations for the results of the evaluation [82].

The single-case study approach has been applied both in social science in general and in software engineering in particular [83]. Single case studies have been used previously in software engineering research as they provide

more flexible procedures and patterns of working that allow the researcher to find out how different issues hold different significance and focus on research identification and interpretation [84, 85, 86, 87]. According to Perry et al. [88] and Flyvbjerg [89], a single case study with one participant is sufficient for generalization. To set up the case study, we followed the activities proposed in Runeson and Höst [82]: case study context, study design, execution and data collection, and data analysis.

Case Study Context. The study was conducted at an application-oriented research institute in Europe. This institute collaborates with others to conduct research and development, aiming to turn original ideas into innovations that benefit society and strengthen the European economy. It consists of more than 70 research units and has over 28,000 employees. The institute specializes in defense and security, information and communication technology, life science, light and surfaces, materials and components, microelectronics, and production. Over 70% of the research projects are collaborations with the private sector or publicly funded commissioned research projects. The remaining projects rely on public funds from governments.

This institute controls a SECO based on an open source platform for next-generation automation with projects related to asset administration shells. This SECO provides a free software platform that enables all interested parties, large and small industries, research institutes, academia, and interested persons to participate in and shape the fourth industrial revolution. It provides common and re-useable Industrie 4.0 components and hosts a multitude of software development kits (SDK) for different programming languages (e.g., Java, Python, .Net, and C++).

Two professionals of the institute participated in this study: the head of the department responsible for this SECO and the SECO project manager. We selected them due to their expertise in the SECO. The department head has more than 15 years of experience, and the SECO project manager has more than five years of experience. The department head holds a PhD, and the project manager holds an M.Sc. The SECO project manager is responsible for managing requirements change and has a deeper and more practical understanding of the problems and challenges faced in the requirements change identification in this SECO, which allows for a richer and more detailed analysis of the results. Table 4 provides the background information about each participant.

ID	Academic degree	Experience	Current position
P1	PhD	5 - 10 years	Head of Department
P2	M.Sc.	5 - 10 years	Project Manager

Table 4: Study #2 - Participants' profile.

Study Design. This study aimed to evaluate SECO-RCI's acceptance from a practical perspective. We revisited some aspects addressed in *Study #1* and introduced new aspects that only those who employed the method could evaluate. Specifically, our focus was to gather information from participants about their learning experiences while using the method, their perception of clarity and understanding, ease of use, usefulness, and impact on job performance. For this study, we defined the following question: **RQ2** - *Is SECO-RCI feasible from a practical perspective?*

For this study, we developed a tool that provides a simplified way of performing the method activities without relying on highly specialized approaches [71]. We made this decision because implementing specialized approaches would require a level of knowledge and experience that the participants currently do not possess. By doing so, we ensured that participants could effectively engage with the method's concepts and activities without being hindered by a lack of prior knowledge. Moreover, this approach allows the participants to focus on understanding the fundamentals of the method and its potential benefits in improving requirements change identification in SECO, setting the basis for improvements. The dynamics of this study initially involved an understanding of the case (where the method would be applied) with the department head and training on the method and the tool with the SECO project manager. After the training, the SECO project manager performed the method activities. The SECO project manager employed the tool to perform the activities of the SECO-RCI method, considering their experience with the SECO described and their knowledge about it.

Execution and Data Collection. The data were collected from June 2024 to August 2022 and emerged from the semi-structured interviews. All the group communications and semi-structured interviews happened online. We used Google Meet as the video conferencing tool and an online questionnaire to support the data collection. The data collection process was divided into three steps:

- Step 1: carrying out a semi-structured interview with the head of the department to define the best strategy to apply SECO-RCI.

- Step 2: application of a questionnaire to identify the SECO project manager’s first impressions regarding the method’s application.
- Step 3: carrying out a semi-structured interview with the SECO project manager to verify SECO-RCI’s acceptance from a practical perspective.

For step 2, we formulated five statements for *Study #2*, using a 5-point Likert scale (*Strongly Agree, Partially Agree, Neutral, Partially Disagree, and Strongly Disagree*) to gather the first impression of the participants. Then, in Step 3, we encouraged the participants to deep into their answers by asking follow-up questions to gain a more comprehensive understanding. Table 5 lists the statements of *Study #2*.

ID	Statement	Aspect	Description
S8	I found the process of learning to use the method to be a positive experience.	Learning experience	It refers to the participant’s process of gaining knowledge related to the use of the method and how intuitive the method is perceived.
S9	The method’s purposes and activities were clear and understandable.	Clarity and understanding	It refers to how easily a participant can understand the method and how clear its activities and related outputs are to them.
S10	I found the method to be easy to use.	Ease of use	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would be free from difficulty.
S11	This method would be useful in supporting me to do my job.	Usefulness	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would produce desirable outcomes.
S12	Applying this method would allow me to perform my job more efficiently.	Impact on job performance	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would improve job efficiency or allow them to accomplish tasks more quickly.

Table 5: Study #2 statements.

Data Analysis. We followed the same qualitative analysis strategy used in Study 1. We recorded and transcribed the interviews to analyze the responses. We provide the complete results of the execution of semi-structured interviews and the questionnaire application in Section 6. The results of our data analysis are discussed in Section 7.

5. The SECO-RCI Method

SECO-RCI is a method for requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and CrowdRE. This method is based on open innovation because it considers user feedback from external actors across multiple

user feedback channels for requirements change identification in SECO and the involvement of external actors that may belong to distinct crowds (SECO niche players) in the review of SECO requirements change requests. This method is based on CrowdRE because it considers user feedback from distinct crowds (SECO niche players) obtained in multiple user feedback channels through (semi-)automated approaches for requirements change identification in SECO and active involvement of the distinct crowds (SECO niche players) in the review of SECO requirements change requests defined based on user feedback obtained in multiple user feedback channels.

SECO-RCI considers characteristics (e.g., keystone, internal and external actors, platform enabling external contributions, and openness) [35], offering a more reasonable approach to handling requirements change in this context. Creating open requirements management systems and constantly listening to user feedback is an important task to incorporate wishes from partners into SECO products or platform [15]. Improving user feedback gathering and analysis from distinct crowds is important in a SECO context [14]. Analyzing user feedback is an approach to support the growth of a sustainable and healthy ecosystem [90]. Several SECO actors rely on this user feedback to make decisions and prioritize their actions [14].

5.1. Overview

SECO-RCI consists of five activities described in Table 6 and presented through a process-deliverable diagram (PDD) in Figure 2. SECO-RCI summarises the findings obtained from SMS and field studies and contains the main activities, sub-activities, and concepts relevant to requirements change identification in SECO. Two roles are mapped in the SECO-RCI method: (i) SECO requirements manager, i.e., professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO, and (ii) SECO niche players, i.e., actors who create value in a SECO. A practical example for each of the method activities is described in the supplementary material [71].

5.2. Identify SECO Open Innovation Practices and SECO User Feedback Channels

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO open innovation practices (e.g., collaboration, co-creation and crowdsourcing) and SECO user feedback channels (e.g., user feedback channels related to the platform and SECO products). User feedback channels can enable several open innovation practices, ensuring that feedback from external actors

Figure 2: PDD of SECO-RCI method.

Table 6: The five steps of the SECO-RCI method.

Activity	Optional?	Description
Identify SECO open innovation practices and SECO user feedback channels	No	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO open innovation practices and SECO user feedback channels, including those allowing open innovation practices.
Perform pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels based on CrowdRE	No	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to create a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification through pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels.
Define SECO requirements change requests	No	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze pattern detection results, extract SECO requirements change requests, and list them in priority order.
Review SECO requirement change requests	Yes	This activity allows SECO niche players to review (i.e., analyze, vote, and prioritize) the SECO requirements change requests list.
Redefine SECO requirements change requests based on SECO niche players' review	Yes	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to redefine the SECO requirements change requests list based on SECO niche players' reviews.

and their users is also analyzed. Therefore, it is positioned as the first activity in the execution of the method, preventing SECO user feedback channels from being neglected.

Analyze SECO Open Innovation Practices. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO open innovation practices. Moreover, it can support the discovery of external actors who can contribute to identifying emergent requirements or requirements change across several SECO user feedback channels.

Identify SECO User Feedback Channels. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO user feedback channels, including those used by external actors and their users through open innovation practices. These SECO user feedback channels can be related to the SECO platform, API, and SECO products. Hence, the user feedback provided through these multiple user feedback channels can be valuable to requirements change identification in SECO.

5.3. Perform Pattern Detection in SECO User Feedback Channels Based on CrowdRE

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to create a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification through pat-

tern detection in SECO user feedback channels. This environment uses semi-automated approaches to gather and analyze user feedback from distinct crowds (i.e., SECO niche players) available on SECO user feedback channels. This activity also aims to perform pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels selected by the requirements manager.

Create CrowdRE Environment. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to create a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification, considering pattern detection between user feedback obtained in SECO user feedback channels. To do so, the SECO requirements manager must select the user feedback channels to perform the pattern detection and define filters (e.g., by keywords or not).

Execute Pattern Detection in SECO User Feedback Channels. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to execute pattern detection in selected SECO user feedback channels. Using data mining techniques and considering the defined filter, user feedback is obtained from selected SECO user feedback channels. After obtaining SECO user feedback, non-relevant content (links, too many spaces, HTML tags, codes, stop-words) is removed. Moreover, lemmatization is applied to the set of user feedback obtained to encompass more texts that contain the keywords. Lemmatization is a process of finding the base morphological form (lemma) of a word [91]. Finally, topic modeling is performed on the obtained SECO user feedback set. After topic generation, the similarity analysis is carried out between user feedback on the same topic, aiming to identify the most similar ones, including user feedback from different projects/products in a SECO. Hence, providing a holistic view to the SECO requirements manager about requirements change requests described in multiple SECO user feedback channels is possible.

5.4. Define SECO Requirements Change Requests

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze the results of pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels, extract SECO requirements change requests, and list them in priority order.

Analyze SECO User Feedback Patterns. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze pattern detection results. The SECO requirements manager must analyze each topic generated and verify the similarity between user feedback on the same topic.

Extract SECO Requirements Change Requests. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to extract SECO requirements change requests based on the pattern detection results in the selected SECO user feedback channels. The SECO requirements manager can register SECO requirements change requests and relate them with a bunch of user feedback that determines them.

List SECO Requirements Change Requests. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to list registered SECO requirements change requests, manage this list (update or delete SECO requirements change requests from the list), and define a priority order for listed SECO requirements change requests.

5.5. Review SECO Requirements Change Requests

This activity allows SECO niche players (distinct SECO crowds) to review the SECO requirements change requests registered by the SECO requirements manager. This review consists of analyzing SECO requirements change requests, voting on whether or not they agree with them, and prioritizing them according to their perspective.

Analyze SECO Requirements Change Requests. This sub-activity allows niche players to analyze the SECO requirements change requests list registered by the SECO requirements manager. SECO niche players can view the SECO requirements change requests list and a bunch of user feedback related to each registered SECO requirements change request. This bunch of user feedback may have been obtained from different SECO user feedback channels, related to multiple projects that coevolve in a SECO, and provided by different SECO actors.

Vote on SECO Requirements Change Requests. This sub-activity allows niche players to vote on the registered SECO requirements change requests. After analyzing them, SECO niche players can vote whether they agree (or not) with these SECO requirements change requests.

Prioritize SECO Requirements Change Requests. This subactivity allows niche players to prioritize SECO requirement change requests they previously voted “Yes” to. SECO niche players can list these SECO requirements change requests in order of priority.

5.6. Redefine SECO Requirements Change Requests Based on SECO Niche Players' Review

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to redefine the SECO requirements change requests list based on SECO niche players' reviews. This redefinition is not mandatory but enables the SECO requirements manager to analyze SECO niche players' reviews, manage SECO requirements change requests, and list them again in priority order.

Analyze SECO Niche Players' Review Results of SECO Requirements Change Requests. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze SECO niche players' review results. The SECO requirements manager can analyze the results regarding the agreement (or not) to the SECO requirements change requests list and the different perspectives of the prioritization.

Manage SECO Requirements Change Requests Based on Niche Players' Review. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to manage (update and delete RCR of the RCR list) the SECO requirements change requests list based on SECO niche players' reviews.

List SECO Requirements Change Requests Based on Niche Players' Review. This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to list SECO requirements change requests in priority order based on SECO niche players' reviews. The SECO requirements manager can reprioritize registered SECO requirements change requests due to possible updates in SECO requirements change requests based on SECO niche players' reviews.

6. Results

The results from the two evaluation studies are presented in this section.

6.1. Study #1

We conducted this study with five experts and introduced them to the method. We then asked for their opinions. Figure 3 shows a summary of the responses from participants about the statements we provided in Table 3. In short, participants generally had a positive perception of SECO-RCI. The upcoming sections contain detailed information about the participants' responses.

Figure 3: *Study #1* - Participants' responses.

6.1.1. Clarity and Understanding (S1)

The majority of participants (4 out of 5) demonstrated consensus regarding the clarity and understanding of the prescriptive activities contained in the method. They attributed this perception to the sequential logic of the activities, in which the output of one activity seamlessly informs the next, contributing to an overall coherent method. P2 stated: *“the activities are clear and understanding”*.

According to some participants, aspects related to how the method is modeled (PDD diagram) and the presentation of scenarios for using the method can impact its clarity and understanding. P3 stated that: *“yes, the activities are clear, but I agree with [omitted] that perhaps the use of BPMN makes the method more intuitive”*. P2 dismissed that: *“for me, the activities are clear, but I am an expert on the subject. I believe that the scenarios that appeared later on could have already appeared since the introduction”*.

6.1.2. Ease of Use (S2)

The majority of participants (4 out of 5) expressed a partial agreement on SECO-RCI's ease of use, indicating a moderate level of ease in performing the activities. P5 claimed that: *“the method is very systematic and intuitive. It is interesting to provide examples like you did because you make the method more operational, explaining how to use each of the steps”*. However, some

experts raised key points of attention during the focus group discussion that were: (i) calculation of similarity between user feedback; (ii) bias related to prioritization by niche players from their perspective; (iii) provision of more examples of how method can be adopted in different SECO.

Participants acknowledged the potential complexity and challenges inherent in niche players' prioritization in SECO (part of activity four of the SECO-RCI). P2 stated that: "*it was not clear to me how to deal with the bias in the sub-activity of prioritizing requests for changes to requirements carried out by niche players?*". P5 claimed that: "*it would be interesting to provide more ecosystem examples on how the method can be adopted. Present examples for very different types of ecosystems*".

6.1.3. Usefulness (S3)

All participants agreed on the usefulness of SECO-RCI. P1 stated that: "*I think that the contribution of the method is also to show a landscape of requirements management in complex environments, in large environments, which are ecosystems, and to show how these things can happen or can be systematized, perhaps even with tools and practices that already exist*". The experts recognized the method's capability to support the requirements change identification in SECO. In this regard, the use of open innovation practices and CrowdRE to base the method for identifying requirements changes in SECO was perceived as positive for its role in addressing the complexities that can arise in such environments. P3 stated that: "*regarding the use of open innovation and crowd, collective intelligence, I think it's fantastic, super interesting, I think it's necessary in SECO*".

Participants appreciated the comprehensive view SECO-RCI offers, recognizing its potential to support requirements change identification in SECO. P1 stated that: "*I think you systematized many things in the method. I think that in some specific situation, someone will want to use the method*". Moreover, participants acknowledged that SECO-RCI is a valuable artifact that describes activities that help identify changes to requirements considering the open and dynamic nature of SECO. In this regard, P5 stated: "*it is important to have levels of abstraction in relation to the identified requirements changes and the authority in relation to them in the ecosystem*".

Participants also argued that applying SECO-RCI in a real context is necessary. P1 claimed that: "*I agree with the method's motivation, but there is a large gap between finding motivation and proposing something for the real world. Ideally, you would instantiate the method in a real context, with*

things that already exist, for example. I know it's difficult to find a large ecosystem to apply it, but there's open source too. For example, you can analyze SECO projects using GitHub Discussion, where people discuss requirements and changes".

6.1.4. Potential to Reduce Effort (S4)

Most participants (3 out of 5) agreed that SECO-RCI has the potential to reduce the effort required for requirements identification in SECO. An argument is that using SECO-RCI can help to identify requirements change of distinct crowds of a SECO. P3 stated that: *"open innovation and CrowdRE expand the scope of requirement change identification, which is important in SECO. Using automated approaches such as in the proposed method will probably reduce effort"*. P5 claimed that: *"niche players have demands that they would certainly love that were implemented on the platform, but often the platform will evolve in another direction"*.

6.1.5. Completeness (S5)

Two participants agreed that carrying out all activities is essential to achieving the method's objectives, two were neutral, and one disagreed. Participants who agreed highlighted that the method may or may not consult the crowd. In other words, it is possible to identify requirements changes through user feedback available in user feedback channels, and it is also possible to validate them through crowd consultation and identify new requirements changes. P2 stated that: *"the method's activities allow the identification of changes considering multiple actors and multiple projects in the ecosystem"*.

Participants who were indifferent about this statement mentioned that applying the method in different types of SECO is necessary to confirm that the activities are sufficient. P3 claimed that: *"Initially, I think they are sufficient, but it would be relevant to analyze them in other SECO"*. P4 stated that: *"they are necessary, but I don't know if they are sufficient, especially concerning SECO domains and the tools used by organizations"*. The participant who disagreed (P1) highlighted that: *"I wonder if there aren't similar and less "bureaucratic" alternatives regarding activities. For example, in open source, the list of requirements is listed and voted on by participants. Currently, on Github Discussion, if a feature is identified in the discussion (forum – mining pattern), it can become an issue that needs to be resolved by the community without the need to go through all these steps. As my basis of comparison is research, I tend to disagree that all activities are necessary"*.

6.1.6. Intention of Use (S6)

All participants agreed that they could use SECO-RCI in future opportunities. They highlighted that SECO-RCI is based on concepts that are important for SECO in literature and practice due to its open and dynamic nature. This suggests that SECO-RCI has the potential to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. P2 highlighted that: *“the method helps someone in the role of manager to identify changes to SECO requirements. It is based on Crowd and open innovation which are useful in many projects in SECO”*.

Participants also suggested activities that could improve the intention to use the method. P3 suggested that: *“it would be relevant to consider in the method a consultation of already consolidated requirements from other similar SECO, success and failure cases of these SECO. Together with the collective intelligence that you obtain with CrowdRE, obtain knowledge of similar SECO that may bring requirements and compare these requirements with success or failure cases of this SECO, which is super important”*. P1 complemented P3 and commented that: *“the day-to-day practices of an ecosystem are very specific. I’ll give you an example, GitHub launched a tool called GitHub Discussion to discuss changes to project requirements, but not even 5% of large GitHub repositories use it. Why? Because they manage requirements differently”*.

6.1.7. Adaptability (S7)

Two participants agreed that the SECO-RCI method is adaptable across different SECO types, two were neutral, and one disagreed. Participants who agreed recognized the potential adaptability of SECO-RCI’s generic activities and acknowledged the method’s ability to address common challenges in requirements change identification in SECO. In addition, they highlighted the method’s potential to provide systematic guidance to requirements change identification in SECO. P3 stated that: *“the method is generic, and I believe it could be used in proprietary, open, and hybrid ecosystems”*.

There was a certain skepticism among some participants regarding the universal applicability of SECO-RCI in all SECO types. P1 stated that: *“being adaptable to all contexts is something very strong in my opinion. There probably must be a counterexample where the method will not be useful”*. P4 mentioned that: *“I have doubts regarding the diversity of application domains, experiences and cultures of organizations”*. P5 claimed that: *“the artifact with the method description does not provide examples of different*

instantiations of the method in different ecosystems (proprietary, open source, mobile, safety-critical domain etc.), so it is impossible to verify the method's adaptability".

6.1.8. How is the acceptance of the SECO-RCI method among experts in the field? (RQ1)

The overall reception of SECO among participants suggests a positive panorama, particularly in terms of its ease of use, usefulness and intention of use. The clarity and understandability of the activities and benefits of potential effort reduction were also considered positive points of the method. A key insight from participant feedback is that SECO-RCI provides a systematic approach to requirements change identification that considers specific characteristics of SECO and is based on important paradigms in this context, open innovation and CrowdRE.

6.2. Study #2

Study #2 involved two professionals: the head of the department and the SECO project manager. The department head explained how the requirements change identification worked in SECO, and the SECO project manager applied the SECO-RCI method in a real case.

We conducted a semi-structured interview with the head of the department to understand better the case to be studied and identify details about the process of identifying changes to requirements in SECO from the department's perspective. Initially, we asked them how the process of requirements change identifications worked at the SECO for which they was responsible. The head of the department explained that: *"there is no uniform approach to identifying changes in requirements. Each project carries it out in its own way"*. They also highlighted that: *"it is the project managers and the product owner who identify changes and document them as assignments on GitHub. If a bug or issue is identified, a notification opens on GitHub"*. Furthermore, the head of the department stated that: *"there is a professional who deals with specific SECO changes. The evolution of SECO is treated as a project and has its own team, whose components are involved in some of SECO's other projects"*.

We then ask the department head what problems he identifies in this process. They highlighted the problem of the lack of a broad view of requirements change requests in SECO that emerge from different projects in multiple SECO communication channels. According to them, the keystone

has difficulty visualizing the origin of SECO requirements change requests. The head of the department stated that: *“I have difficulty seeing where the ends are tied. I would like to see it in different degrees of detail. If I want to see this, I have to go one by one to check. As a manager, I have to trust what my project manager seniors say”*.

Finally, we asked the department head what could change in this process, considering the open and dynamic nature of SECO. They responded that: *“the degree of dependence I have on different people to have a central vision of SECO and visualize possible changes. Some automatization could improve this”*.

The SECO project manager applied the SECO-RCI method to a real case, using a tool that supports the instantiation of the method. As mentioned in Section 4, the tool offers a method instantiation. After the SECO project manager received training on the SECO-RCI method and the tool, we request that they:

1. Create an environment for requirements change identification by adding at least two GitHub repositories of inter-projects of their SECO;
2. Perform pattern detection in issues from selected repositories for the registered environment;
3. Analyze the results of pattern detection to identify requirement change requests that may have been requested in the different selected user feedback channels;
4. Register requirements change requests for the SECO analyzed;
5. List requirements change requests in priority order;
6. Export the CSV file from the list of registered requirements change requests.

In this study, the participant executed all activities to identify requirements change using open innovation practices (i.e., considering user feedback of external actors in open user feedback channels to identify requirements change) and CrowdRE (i.e., using a semiautomated approach to identify validated requirements change from distinct crowds of SECO). Therefore, consultation with distinct crowds of SECO has not been executed.

6.2.1. Learning Experience (S8)

The participant reported that learning the method was positive in several moments, but in some moments, they needed to refer to the description of

the method to understand better what he really needed to do in each activity. For this reason, he/she neither agreed nor disagreed on the process of learning to use the method to be a positive experience. However, they also highlighted that the learning curve for applying the method was not steep. The SECO project manager highlighted that: *“learning the method included a document describing the method that contained a practical example and a document demonstrating the tool. When I had difficulty understanding what needed to be done in the activity, I looked at the figures, an example of this activity being performed in the tool”*. Moreover, the participant identified opportunities for improvement that could make the method learning experience more positive. For example, they mentioned that the method description was long and contained content repeated in the text, which could confuse the user. The SECO project manager claimed that: *“there are activities that have three sub-activities, and there are texts that are repeated, and this left me a little confused about what I should do in each of them”*. The participant reported that it is important that whoever applies the method understands it very well and relates it to the context of their ecosystem. Moreover, they expressed optimism that familiarity with the method would be gained through continued use and experience.

6.2.2. Clarity and Understanding (S9)

The participant agreed that the purposes and activities of SECO-RCI are clear and comprehensive. However, they highlighted that it would be important for the activity and sub-activity to highlight what is expected as an input and output. The SECO project manager suggested: *“something that could be improved in the description of activities would be to present a short initial text informing what that activity needs as input and what its result will be, that is, what is expected from the output of that activity”*. This feedback offers practical considerations for refining the method and improving their clarity and understanding.

6.2.3. Ease of Use (S10)

The participant agreed that SECO-RCI is easy to use. They pointed out challenges that emerged in specific activities, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement in the method. As strengths, the participant highlighted that the tool helps apply the method, facilitating its use. Furthermore, they mentioned that the activities and sub-activities refer to practices with which they are familiar, e.g., analyzing issues in GitHub to identify requirements

change. The SECO project manager claimed that: *“I liked the way the pattern detection results can be visualized. This allowed me to easily identify which feedback was related to a requirements change and which was not”*. As areas for improvement, the participant mentioned that the method did not describe how pattern detection is carried out and how environment settings related to keyword filters and user feedback status can impact the analysis. The SECO project manager mentioned that: *“I did several tests to familiarize myself with the tool and the method’s activities. I realized that the keywords defined when creating the environment impact detecting patterns in the feedback retrieved, but it is not too clear in the method description”*.

6.2.4. Usefulness (S11)

The participant agreed with the method’s utility in their daily tasks. The SECO project manager acknowledged its role in supporting the requirements change identification in SECO and highlighted that: *“I believe it could be useful. However, it would require more interaction with the tool to learn the best way to use it, e.g., the filters and consequent results (grouping of tickets)”*. The participant also mentioned that the method often requires the manager to know more technical terms from SECO projects so that he can correctly direct the analysis by choosing keywords. The SECO project manager stated that: *“The manager needs to know the projects technically to define the most appropriate keywords. This works for small project groups, as was my case. However, for larger project groups in which the manager does not have this prior knowledge, it may be that the information generated is too generic”*.

6.2.5. Impact on Job Performance (S12)

The participant neither agreed nor disagreed that utilizing the method would enhance their job efficiency. They highlighted that the tool grouped feedback related to a specific problem that could generate changes to requirements in the ecosystem. However, the participant tried to configure the CrowdRE environment keyword filter to achieve this result. The SECO project manager stated that: *“see the potential, but I am not convinced if the tool would be able to classify and group the tickets/issues in the best way without the manager’s prior knowledge. I believe that if the tool also showed the number of occurrences of a certain term that could be related to a requirements change, it would be excellent. This would greatly help the manager to verify the importance of that change for SECO. The manager often looks*

for changes to requirements in GitHub issues to analyze them. If the tool could show this to him concerning the number of times that changes appear, it would be super interesting”.

6.2.6. Is SECO-RCI feasible from a practical perspective? (RQ2)

Based on the findings of Study #2, we gained valuable insights into the practical feasibility of SECO-RCI. One key consideration that emerged is the crucial need for a specific tool to carry out the method activities successfully. Their use is important because of the open and dynamic nature of SECO, which involves user feedback from several communication channels. Acceptance of SECO-RCI by the participant and recognition of its usefulness can be seen as a positive aspect of its practical applicability. The participant emphasized the potential for continual improvement and refinement of results through consistent application of the method. This statement underscores the dynamic nature of SECO-RCI, suggesting that with ongoing use, it can address the identification of changing requirements in SECO and promote advancements in requirements management in SECO.

7. Discussion

In this section, we discuss our research’s main findings and implications and propose how researchers and practitioners can use SECO-RCI.

7.1. Main Findings and Lessons Learned

We gathered insights and reflections along the process of designing and evaluating SECO-RCI, as described next:

- **Requirements change identification in SECO requires the involvement of experts in the SECO domain and technical aspects of the projects:** Both evaluation studies highlighted the importance of a deep understanding of the SECO and the projects that coevolve in this environment while dealing with requirements change identification. The participants stated that this is fundamental for adequately applying SECO-RCI. Bogart et al. [12] corroborates this finding by stating that changes to one product can have cascading effects on several others in SECO, and a holistic view of the SECO from domain experts is necessary to avoid conflicts. According to Matute et al. [19], any discernible (and sometimes even apparently trivial) change in a software product will affect, for better or worse, its ecosystem.

- **The value of SECO-RCI increases with continuous use:** From the participants' comments, it becomes apparent that the method's value increases with continual use. As the professionals gain more experience with the method, they can more effectively identify the requirements change in SECO, considering their open and dynamic nature. The continuous application of the method allows the constant identification of keywords related to the multiple projects that co-evolve in SECO, which can result in greater effectiveness in identifying changes to requirements. Bogart et al. [12] mentioned that technical debt, bugs, new features, or rippling upstream changes trigger breaking SECO changes. For the authors, central planning in software engineering is increasingly giving way to decentralized development in SECO, in which developers build on a rich set of external contributions, from libraries to community documentation.
- **The use of SECO-RCI increases with the scale of SECO:** Applying SECO-RCI to large SECO introduces a high level of complexity due to the multitude of user feedback spread in several user feedback channels. Such circumstances create a highly complex scenario requiring careful attention. Bogart et al. [12] stated that SECO actors (e.g., internal and external developers) can reuse and build upon others' contributions, often aided by package management tools that support finding, installing, and publishing third-party packages in the ecosystem. According to the authors, software development in such a decentralized environment can be challenging and expose friction among loosely organized parties.

Regarding **lessons learned**, during the conduction of the evaluation studies, we recognized the importance of including more professionals in the evaluation process. Professionals with a background in Information Technology (IT) bring valuable technical expertise. However, we included domain experts in the evaluation, and with their specialized knowledge, they provided additional insights concerning specific particularities, which was important in evaluating the method's adaptability. Another important lesson was the need to develop a tool that can encompass all method activities clearly, allowing participants to express their opinions on SECO-RCI without limitations.

7.2. Implications for Practitioners and Researchers

This study presents implications for **practitioners**, as presented next:

- **Improvement of requirements change identification in SECO:** Using SECO-RCI can lead to an improvement in requirements change identification in SECO. Executing the activities of the method, professionals can identify requirements change and define requirements change requests, considering user feedback spread in multiple SECO user feedback channels.
- **Improvement of the holistic view of the SECO regarding changes:** SECO-RCI allows professionals to have a holistic view regarding requirements changes that may affect different projects in SECO or the common technological platform. By offering this comprehensive view of requirements change in SECO, SECO-RCI allows professionals to make well-informed decisions, prioritize actions more efficiently, and coordinate their efforts more effectively.
- **Improvement of requirements communication:** SECO-RCI was perceived as a facilitator of effective communication among multiple SECO actors. It can help promote a shared understanding concerning requirements change, collaboration and co-creation, improved decision-making, and stakeholder engagement.

During the conduction of this study, we also identified implications for researchers, as in the following:

- **Change-oriented perspective for future research:** The use of SECO-RCI provides a comprehensive view of the SECO concerning requirements change identification. This comprehensive perspective can also improve other requirements management subprocesses.
- **Adaptability to diverse SECO types:** SECO-RCI can serve as a foundation for future research on adaptability in different SECO types. Researchers can explore how the method can be tailored and customized to specific domains. This research can lead to developing domain-specific extensions or variations of the method, enabling its effective application in a more significant range of SECO.

8. Threats and Limitations

8.1. Threats to Credibility and Reliability

In contrast to quantitative studies, qualitative studies are more prone to threats to credibility than to validity [92, 93]. The matters of validity and

reliability in qualitative research rely on the meticulousness, thoroughness, and honesty employed by the researchers throughout the data collection and analysis procedures [94]. Thus, we outline the potential threats to external and internal credibility in the following.

Internal credibility refers to the credibility of interpretations and conclusions within the underlying setting or group [95]. When conducting interviews and transcriptions, we can incur risks when interpreting participants' responses according to our perspective instead of considering the participant's perspective. This threat is related to interpretative validity, which is a potential threat to the internal credibility of this study. To mitigate this threat, we defined an interview guide with clear and objective questions presented during the interviews, comprising all concepts related to these questions. We also encouraged participants to reflect deeply on their answers. In addition, while the first author of this study performed the main coding, the other three authors, with more than 15 years in SE, were extensively involved in double-checking the results and ensuring the compliance of the final dataset (two of them with 10 years of experience in leading large software projects in industry as well as in working in consultancy in the field).

External credibility refers to the degree to which the findings of a study can be generalized across different contexts [95]. The number, experience, and the fact that all participants worked with a single scenario of SECO are potential external threats to this study. To mitigate such threats, we selected professionals and experts with different backgrounds and experience in requirements management in SECO. This strategy contributed to a more significant variety of information with different perspectives. We also carried out studies from distinct perspectives. The first study focused on participants' perceptions of the method through demonstration and explanation. In contrast, the second one took a more practical approach, with one participant using the method and offering their opinions based on a practical experience.

8.2. Limitations

Acknowledging that our evaluation is limited to only one specific scenario is essential. While our findings and conclusions provide valuable insights into that particular context, validating the results in other contexts is crucial. By conducting studies in multiple contexts, we can assess the robustness and applicability of our findings across various scenarios. This assessment

helps establish a broader understanding of the framework’s effectiveness and potential limitations in different real-world situations.

Furthermore, exploring different contexts can uncover insights and nuances our studies might not capture. It can shed light on new challenges and contextual factors that may influence the implementation and outcomes of the method. Hence, such additional validation can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the framework’s capabilities and limitations.

9. Conclusions

Requirements change identification in SECO poses significant challenges due to the complexity and interconnectedness of several components, the involvement of multiple stakeholders, and the dynamic nature of user needs and technological advancements. Traditional methods often fail to capture these evolving requirements promptly, leading to delays, increased costs, and reduced product quality. SECO-RCI seeks to address these issues by providing structured activities that support effectively identifying requirements change based on the open innovation and CrowdRE paradigms, considering the dynamic and open nature of SECO. By leveraging the collective intelligence of a diverse and engaged community, organizations can more effectively identify, validate, and prioritize requirements changes in SECO. This collaborative approach not only enhances the agility and responsiveness of software development processes but also fosters innovation, ensuring that the final product better meets the needs of its users and remains competitive in a rapidly changing environment.

By using SECO-RCI, professionals can better understand SECO characteristics that differentiate it from other software development contexts and the requirements change identification in this context. Moreover, our method enables more effective requirements communication among the multiple actors of distinct crowds of a SECO regarding requirements change, ensuring everyone is on the same page. It also supports decision-making regarding the implementation of these requirements changes.

As future work, we emphasize the need for further studies with an expanded participant base to enhance the robustness of our findings. Moreover, we can investigate how the method might be adapted or extended to meet specific domains. However, it is imperative to highlight the ongoing challenges associated with identifying and selecting appropriate scenarios for experimentation in SECO. The inherent complexity and uniqueness of SECO

often make it challenging to obtain a diverse and representative set of scenarios for comprehensive evaluation.

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Data availability

The authors declare that the data supporting the findings of this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12600872>

References

- [1] S. A. Afaq, M. Faisal, An efficient approach for software requirement change identification, *Webology* 18 (2021) 1919–1926.
- [2] K. Madampe, R. Hoda, J. Grundy, Supporting emotional intelligence, productivity and team goals while handling software requirements changes, *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology* 33 (2024). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3664600>.
- [3] S. Jayatilleke, R. Lai, K. Reed, A method of requirements change analysis, *Requirements Engineering* 23 (2018) 493–508. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-017-0277-7>.
- [4] M. Kausar, A. W. Muhammad, R. Jabbar, M. Ishtiaq, Key challenges of requirement change management in the context of global software development: systematic literature review, *Pakistan Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* 30 (2022) 41–51.
- [5] F. Mehmood, S. Zulfqar, Effect of human related factors on requirements change management in offshore software development outsourcing: A theoretical framework, *Software Computing and Machine Intelligence Journal* 1 (2021) 36–52.

- [6] N. Ali, R. Lai, A method of requirements change management for global software development, *Information and Software Technology* 70 (2016) 49–67. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2015.09.005>.
- [7] J. Shah, N. Kama, N. A. A. Bakar, Z. Bhutto, Software requirement change effort estimation model prototype tool for software development phase, *International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications* 10 (2019) 9–19.
- [8] K. Madampe2023, R. Hoda, J. Grundy, The emotional roller coaster of responding to requirements changes in software engineering, *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 49 (2023) 1171–1187. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2022.3172925>.
- [9] R. Fatima, F. Zeshan, A. Ahmad, M. Hamid, A. Ahmad, S. A. Tahir, Software requirements change prediction model, in: *2021 International Conference on Decision Aid Sciences and Application*, IEEE, Sakheer, Bahrain, 2021, pp. 607–612. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/DASA53625.2021.9682217>.
- [10] D. Albuquerque, E. Guimaraes, M. Perkusich, A. Costa, E. Dantas, F. Ramos, H. Almeida, Defining agile requirements change management: a mapping study, in: *35th Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2020, p. 1421–1424. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3341105.3374095>.
- [11] M. A. Akbar, A. A. Khan, S. Mahmood, S. Rafi, A vision of devops requirements change management standardization, in: *2022 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability, and Security Companion*, IEEE, Guangzhou, China, 2022, pp. 587–592. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/QRS-C57518.2022.00094>.
- [12] C. Bogart, C. Kästner, J. Herbsleb, F. Thung, How to break an api: cost negotiation and community values in three software ecosystems, in: *2016 24th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2016, p. 109–120. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/2950290.2950325>.

- [13] D. Damian, J. Linåker, D. Johnson, T. Clear, K. Blincoe, Challenges and strategies for managing requirements selection in software ecosystems, *IEEE Software* 38 (2021) 76–87. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2021.3105044>.
- [14] B. Ghimire, Z. S. Li, D. Damian, Understanding user feedback in software ecosystems: A study on challenges and mitigation strategies, in: *Software Business*, Springer, Cham, Germany, 2023, pp. 132–147. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53227-6_10.
- [15] S. Jansen, A focus area maturity model for software ecosystem governance, *Information and Software Technology* 118 (2020) 106219. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2019.106219>.
- [16] J. Axelsson, M. Skoglund, Quality assurance in software ecosystems: A systematic literature mapping and research agenda, *Journal of Systems and Software* 114 (2016) 69–81. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2015.12.020>.
- [17] M. den Besten, C. Amrit, A. Capiluppi, G. Robles, Collaboration and innovation dynamics in software ecosystems: A technology management research perspective, *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* 68 (2021) 1532–1537. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2020.3015969>.
- [18] J. Linåker, B. Regnell, D. Damian, A method for analyzing stakeholders’ influence on an open source software ecosystem’s requirements engineering process, *Requirements Engineering* 25 (2020) 115–130. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-019-00310-3>.
- [19] G. Matute, A. Cheung, S. Chasins, Change in Software Ecosystems, in: *Plateau Workshop*, 2022, pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1184/R1/19799314.v1>.
- [20] A. Vegendla, A. N. Duc, S. Gao, G. Sindre, A systematic mapping study on requirements engineering in software ecosystems, *Journal of Information Technology Research* 11 (2018) 49–69. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4018/JITR.2018010104>.
- [21] E. Knauss, A. Yussuf, K. Blincoe, D. Damian, A. Knauss, Continuous clarification and emergent requirements flows in open-commercial

- software ecosystems, *Requirements Engineering* 23 (2018) 97–117. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-016-0259-1>.
- [22] G. Alamer, S. Alyahya, A proposed approach to crowd selection in crowdsourced requirements engineering for mobile apps, in: *7th International Conference on Information Systems Engineering*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, USA, 2023, pp. 1–5. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3573926.3573927>.
- [23] T. Wang, T. Qi, X. Zhou, X. Xin, Idea generation performance in open innovation communities: The role of user interaction, *Information & Management* 61 (2024) 103930. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2024.103930>.
- [24] D. Johnson, J. Tizard, D. Damian, K. Blincoe, T. Clear, Open CrowdRE challenges in software ecosystems, in: *2020 4th International Workshop on Crowd-Based Requirements Engineering*, Zurich, Switzerland, 2020, pp. 1–4. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/CrowdRE51214.2020.00007>.
- [25] E. C. Groen, J. Doerr, S. Adam, Towards crowd-based requirements engineering: A research preview, in: *Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality*, Springer, Cham, Germany, 2015, pp. 247–253. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16101-3_16.
- [26] E. C. Groen, N. Seyff, R. Ali, F. Dalpiaz, J. Doerr, E. Guzman, M. Hosseini, J. Marco, M. Oriol, A. Perini, M. Stade, The crowd in requirements engineering: The landscape and challenges, *IEEE Software* 34 (2017) 44–52. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2017.33>.
- [27] O. Barbosa, R. P. Santos, C. Alves, C. Werner, S. Jansen, A systematic mapping study on software ecosystems from a three-dimensional perspective, in: S. Jansen, S. Brinkkemper, M. Cusumano (Eds.), *Software Ecosystems: Analyzing and Managing Business Networks in the Software Industry*, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2013, pp. 59–81. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781781955628.00011>.
- [28] K. Manikas, Revisiting software ecosystems research: a longitudinal literature study, *Journal of Systems and Software* 117 (2016) 84–103. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2016.02.003>.

- [29] D. G. Messerschmitt, C. Szyperski, *Software Ecosystem: Understanding an Indispensable Technology and Industry*, MIT press, 2003.
- [30] J. Bosch, From software product lines to software ecosystems, in: 13th International Software Product Line Conference, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, USA, 2009, pp. 111–119.
- [31] S. Jansen, A. Finkelstein, S. Brinkkemper, A sense of community: A research agenda for software ecosystems, in: 31st International Conference on Software Engineering, IEEE, Vancouver, Canada, 2009, pp. 187–190. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE-COMPANION.2009.5070978>.
- [32] M. Lungu, M. Lanza, T. Gîrba, R. Robbes, The small project observatory: Visualizing software ecosystems, *Science of Computer Programming* 75 (2010) 264–275. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scico.2009.09.004>.
- [33] T. Mens, C. D. Roover, An introduction to software ecosystems, in: T. Mens, C. De Roover, A. Cleve (Eds.), *Software Ecosystems: Tooling and Analytics*, Springer, Cham, Germany, 2023, pp. 1–29. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-36060-2_1.
- [34] K. Manikas, K. M. Hansen, Software ecosystems – a systematic literature review, *Journal of Systems and Software* 86 (2013) 1294–1306. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2012.12.026>.
- [35] D. Lettner, F. Angerer, H. Prähofer, P. Grünbacher, A case study on software ecosystem characteristics in industrial automation software, in: 2014 International Conference on Software and System Process, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, USA, 2014, pp. 40–49. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/2600821.2600826>.
- [36] H. Jeronimo Junior, C. Werner, A systematic mapping on the relations between systems-of-systems and software ecosystems, in: 9th Workshop on Distributed Software Development, Software Ecosystems and Systems-of-Systems, Brazil, 2015, pp. 65–72.
- [37] I. Figalist, C. Elsner, J. Bosch, H. H. Olsson, Scaling agile beyond organizational boundaries: Coordination challenges in software ecosystems, in: *Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Pro-*

- gramming, Springer, Cham, Germany, 2019, pp. 189–206. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19034-7_12.
- [38] M. Che, D. E. Perry, Architectural design decisions in open software development: A transition to software ecosystems, in: 2014 23rd Australian Software Engineering Conference, Milsons Point, NSW, Australia, 2014, pp. 58–61. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ASWEC.2014.37>.
- [39] M. A. Akbar, S. Mahmood, A. Alsanad, M. Shafiq, A. Gumaiei, A. A.-A. Alsanad, Organization type and size based identification of requirements change management challenges in global software development, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 94089–94111. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2995238>.
- [40] N. Nurmuliani, D. Zowghi, S. Powell, Analysis of requirements volatility during software development life cycle, in: 2004 Australian Software Engineering Conference, IEEE, Melbourne, VIC, Australia, 2004, pp. 28–37. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ASWEC.2004.1290455>.
- [41] K. Madampe, R. Hoda, J. Grundy, A faceted taxonomy of requirements changes in agile contexts, *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 48 (2022) 3737–3752. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2021.3104732>.
- [42] M. A. Akbar, J. Sang, Nasrullah, A. A. Khan, S. Mahmood, S. F. Qadri, H. Hu, H. Xiang, Success factors influencing requirements change management process in global software development, *Journal of Computer Languages* 51 (2019) 112–130. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.col.2018.12.005>.
- [43] A. A. Khan, M. A. Akbar, Systematic literature review and empirical investigation of motivators for requirements change management process in global software development, *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process* 32 (2020) e2242. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.2242>.
- [44] H. W. Chesbrough, *Open innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*, Harvard Business Press, 2003.
- [45] G. Valença, N. Lacerda, M. E. Rebelo, C. Alves, C. R. B. de Souza, On the benefits of corporate hackathons for software ecosystems – a

- systematic mapping study, in: *Product-Focused Software Process Improvement*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019, pp. 367–382.
- [46] J. Linåker, P. Rempel, B. Regnell, P. Mäder, How firms adapt and interact in open source ecosystems: Analyzing stakeholder influence and collaboration patterns, in: *Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality*, Springer, Cham, Germany, 2016, pp. 63–81. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-30282-9_5.
- [47] E. Papatheocharous, J. Andersson, J. Axelsson, Ecosystems and open innovation for embedded systems: A systematic mapping study, in: *Software Business*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2015, pp. 81–95.
- [48] J. Linåker, B. Regnell, H. Munir, Requirements engineering in open innovation: A research agenda, in: *2015 International Conference on Software and System Process*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, USA, 2015, pp. 208–212. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/2785592.2795370>.
- [49] J. Linåker, H. Munir, P. Runeson, B. Regnell, C. Schrewelius, A survey on the perception of innovation in a large product-focused software organization, in: *Software Business*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2015, pp. 66–80.
- [50] J. Linåker, K. Wnuk, Requirements analysis and management for benefiting openness, in: *IEEE 24th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops*, IEEE, Beijing, China, 2016, pp. 344–349. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/REW.2016.062>.
- [51] S. Fernandez, R. B. Svensson, A survey of practitioners use of open innovation, in: *43rd Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications*, IEEE, Vienna, Austria, 2017, pp. 305–312. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/SEAA.2017.52>.
- [52] E. C. Groen, M. Ochs, CrowdRE, user feedback and GDPR: Towards tackling GDPR implications with adequate technical and organizational measures in an effort-minimal way, in: *2019 IEEE 27th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops*, IEEE, Jeju, South

- Korea, 2019, pp. 180–185. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/REW.2019.00038>.
- [53] R. Santos, E. C. Groen, K. Villela, An overview of user feedback classification approaches, in: 2019 Joint REFSQ Workshops, Doctoral Symposium, Research Method Track, and Poster Track, co-located with the 23rd International Conference on Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality, CEUR-WS.org, Essen, Germany, 2019, pp. 357–369.
- [54] J. Tizard, T. Rietz, X. Liu, K. Blincoe, Voice of the users: an extended study of software feedback engagement, *Requirements Engineering* 27 (2022) 293–315. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-021-00357-1>.
- [55] D. Dzvoniar, S. Krusche, R. Alkadhi, B. Bruegge, Context-aware user feedback in continuous software evolution, in: 2016 IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Continuous Software Evolution and Delivery, Austin, USA, 2016, pp. 12–18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/2896941.2896952>.
- [56] C. Wang, M. Daneva, M. van Sinderen, P. Liang, A systematic mapping study on crowdsourced requirements engineering using user feedback, *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process* 31 (2019) e2199. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.2199>.
- [57] F. M. Kifetew, A. Perini, A. Susi, A. Siena, D. Muñante, I. Morales-Ramirez, Automating user-feedback driven requirements prioritization, *Information and Software Technology* 138 (2021) 106635. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2021.106635>.
- [58] J. Tizard, P. Devine, H. Wang, K. Blincoe, A software requirements ecosystem: Linking forum, issue tracker, and FAQs for requirements management, *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 49 (2023) 2381–2393. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2022.3219458>.
- [59] S. van Oordt, E. Guzman, On the role of user feedback in software evolution: A practitioners’ perspective, in: 2021 IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference, IEEE, Notre Dame, USA, 2021, pp. 221–232. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/RE51729.2021.00027>.

- [60] K. Villela, A. Hess, M. Koch, R. Falcao, E. C. Groen, J. Dörr, C. N. Valero, A. Ebert, Towards ubiquitous RE: A perspective on requirements engineering in the era of digital transformation, in: IEEE 26th International Requirements Engineering Conference, IEEE, Banff, Canada, 2018, pp. 205–216. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/RE.2018.00029>.
- [61] K. Villela, E. C. Groen, J. Doerr, Ubiquitous requirements engineering: A paradigm shift that affects everyone, IEEE Software 36 (2019) 8–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2018.2883876>.
- [62] S. L. Lim, A. Finkelstein, Anticipating change in requirements engineering, in: P. Avgeriou, J. Grundy, J. G. Hall, P. Lago, I. Mistrík (Eds.), Relating Software Requirements and Architectures, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 17–34. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-21001-3_3.
- [63] A. Amaral, F. de Franco Rosa, Method for assessing the potential impact of changes in software requirements of agile methodologies based projects, in: Human Interface and the Management of Information, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2023, pp. 3–21.
- [64] R. J. Wieringa, What Is Design Science?, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2014, pp. 3–11. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-43839-8_1.
- [65] S. Brinkkemper, Method engineering: engineering of information systems development methods and tools, Information and Software Technology 38 (1996) 275–280. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0950-5849\(95\)01059-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0950-5849(95)01059-9), method Engineering and Meta-Modelling.
- [66] B. Henderson-Sellers, J. Ralyté, P. J. Ågerfalk, M. Rossi, Situational method engineering, Springer, 2014. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41467-1>.
- [67] P. Malcher, E. Silva, D. Viana, R. Santos, What do we know about requirements management in software ecosystems?, Requirements Engineering 28 (2023) 567–593. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-023-00407-w>.

- [68] P. Malcher, D. Viana, P. O. Antonino, R. P. Santos, Investigating open innovation practices to support requirements management in software ecosystems, in: *Software Business*, Springer, Cham, Germany, 2023, pp. 35–50. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53227-6_3.
- [69] P. Malcher, D. Viana, P. O. Antonino, R. P. dos Santos, Investigating user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in software ecosystems, *Empirical Software Engineering* (2024). Under submission.
- [70] P. Malcher, D. Viana, P. O. Antonino, R. P. dos Santos, Towards an understanding of requirements management in software ecosystems, *Journal of Systems and Software* (2024). Under submission.
- [71] P. Malcher, D. Viana, P. O. Antonino, R. P. Santos, Replication package for: A method for requirements change identification in software ecosystems, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12600872>.
- [72] W. C. Adams, Conducting semi-structured interviews, in: K. Newcomer, H. Hatry, J. Wholey (Eds.), *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2015, pp. 492–505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19>.
- [73] F. Davis, Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology, *MIS Quartely* 13 (1989) 319–340.
- [74] J. Kontio, J. Bragge, L. Lehtola, The focus group method as an empirical tool in software engineering, in: F. Shull, J. Singer, D. I. K. Sjøberg (Eds.), *Guide to Advanced Empirical Software Engineering*, Springer London, London, 2008, pp. 93–116. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84800-044-5_4.
- [75] S. B. Merriam, E. J. Tisdell, *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*, John Wiley & Sons, 2015.
- [76] S. Baltés, P. Ralph, Sampling in software engineering research: A critical review and guidelines, *Empirical Software Engineering* 27 (2022) 94. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-021-10072-8>.
- [77] F. Shull, J. Singer, D. I. Sjøberg, *Guide to advanced empirical software engineering*, volume 93, Springer, 2008. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84800-044-5>.

- [78] M. Hennink, B. N. Kaiser, Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests, *Social Science & Medicine* 292 (2022) 114523. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114523>.
- [79] A. Strauss, J. Corbin, *Basics of qualitative research*, Sage Publications, 1990.
- [80] R. Wieringa, M. Daneva, Six strategies for generalizing software engineering theories, *Science of Computer Programming* 101 (2015) 136–152. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scico.2014.11.013>.
- [81] R. K. Yin, Validity and generalization in future case study evaluations, *Evaluation* 19 (2013) 321–332. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389013497081>.
- [82] P. Runeson, M. Höst, Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering, *Empirical Software Engineering* 14 (2009) 131–164. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-008-9102-8>.
- [83] A. S. Al-Ahmad, H. Kahtan, Y. I. Alzoubi, Overview on case study penetration testing models evaluation, *Emerging Science Journal* 7 (2023) 1019–1036. doi:<https://doi.org/10.28991/ESJ-2023-07-03-025>.
- [84] C. Seaman, Qualitative methods in empirical studies of software engineering, *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 25 (1999) 557–572. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/32.799955>.
- [85] G. K. Hanssen, A longitudinal case study of an emerging software ecosystem: Implications for practice and theory, *Journal of Systems and Software* 85 (2012) 1455–1466. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2011.04.020>.
- [86] K.-J. Stol, B. Fitzgerald, Two’s company, three’s a crowd: a case study of crowdsourcing software development, in: *36th International Conference on Software Engineering*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2014, p. 187–198. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/2568225.2568249>.
- [87] I. F. da Silva, P. A. da Mota Silveira Neto, P. O’Leary, E. S. Almeida, S. R. de Lemos Meira, Software product line scoping and requirements

- engineering in a small and medium-sized enterprise: An industrial case study, *Journal of Systems and Software* 88 (2014) 189–206. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2013.10.040>.
- [88] D. E. Perry, S. E. Sim, S. Easterbrook, Case studies for software engineers, in: 28th International Conference on Software Engineering, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2006, p. 1045–1046. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/1134285.1134497>.
- [89] B. Flyvbjerg, Five misunderstandings about case-study research, *Qualitative inquiry* 12 (2006) 219–245. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800405284363>.
- [90] A. Foundjem, Cross-distribution feedback in software ecosystems, in: IEEE/ACM 42nd International Conference on Software Engineering Workshops, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2020, p. 723–724. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3387940.3392188>.
- [91] R. Pramana, Debora, J. J. Subroto, A. A. S. Gunawan, Anderies, Systematic literature review of stemming and lemmatization performance for sentence similarity, in: 2022 IEEE 7th International Conference on Information Technology and Digital Applications (ICITDA), 2022, pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICITDA55840.2022.9971451>.
- [92] M. Greiler, M.-A. Storey, A. Noda, An actionable framework for understanding and improving developer experience, *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 49 (2022) 1411–1425. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2022.3175660>.
- [93] B. B. Ribeiro, C. Costa, R. P. Santos, Understanding and analyzing factors that affect merge conflicts from the perspective of software developers, *Journal of Software Engineering Research and Development* 10 (2022) 12:1–12:17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5753/jserd.2022.2576>.
- [94] C. Robson, *Real World Research - A Resource for Social Scientists and Practitioner-Researchers*, Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, 2002.
- [95] A. J. Onwuegbuzie, N. L. Leech, Validity and Qualitative Research: An Oxymoron?, *Quality & Quantity* 41 (2007) 233–249.